

rare earth metal ions in the test electrolytic solution were kept constant at 1.0 M, 0.01% and 2 mM, respectively. The ligand concentration was varied from 1.0 mM to 10 mM. The ionic strength was fixed at 1.0 M, adjusting with potassium chloride. Hydrochloric acid was used to adjust the pH of the solution at 2.4 ± 0.02 .

An automatic pen recording (C. I. C., Baroda, India) polarograph was used to record the polarograms. The capillary used had an m value of 2.15 mg/sec and drop time of 3.0 sec, when measured in an air free 1.0 M potassium chloride at 31.0 cm effective height of the mercury column. Pure nitrogen gas was used for deoxygenating the solution before recording the polarograms. All measurements were carried out at 25 and 35° in thermostat.

Results and Discussion

Praseodymium(III) and neodymium(III) give well defined three electron reversible reduction waves at pH 2.4⁶⁻⁷ in 1.0 M potassium chloride, with 0.01% gelatin being used as a maximum suppressor. The nature of the waves for metal ions and their complexes was found to be diffusion controlled as revealed from linear plots of i_d vs \sqrt{h} . The reduction of praseodymium(III) and neodymium(III) at pH 2.4 ± 0.02 were at -1.81 V and -1.79 V vs SCE. The log plot slope values for the metal ions and their complexes was 20 ± 1 mV indicating the reversibility of the electrode process.

The half wave potential shifted to more negative values on gradual increase of ligand concentration. A Lingane⁸ treatment of the data revealed the formation of 1 : 1 complexes for praseodymium(III) and neodymium(III) with glutamic acid. The values of stability constant and thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—METAL LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS OF THE COMPLEXES AT $\mu=1.0$ M POTASSIUM CHLORIDE

		25°	35°
Metal ligand stability constant (log K)	Praseodymium(III)	4.00	3.81
	Neodymium(III)	5.30	5.11
Change in enthalpy (ΔH) in k cal/mole	Praseodymium(III)	-8.04*	
	Neodymium(III)	-3.21*	
Change in free energy (ΔG) in k cal/mole	Praseodymium(III)	-5.52	-5.43
	Neodymium(III)	-7.31	-7.29
Change in entropy (ΔS) in cal/degree/mole	Praseodymium(III)	-8.41	-8.42
	Neodymium(III)	-3.00	-2.29

* For the difference of 10°.

The order of stability constants of the metal ions is praseodymium(III) < neodymium(III). The increase of stability constants from praseodymium(III) to neodymium(III) is mainly due to lanthanide contraction.

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Thermodynamics and Stability Constants of Ce(III) Complexes with Crotonic, Cinnamic, Itaconic and Citraconic Acids :

A Polarographic Study

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POLAROGRAPHY has been used for the complexation study of Pr(III) and Nd(III) with some unsaturated acids¹⁻⁴. In continuation, we now report thermodynamic parameters and stability constants of the complexes of Ce(III) with crotonic, cinnamic, itaconic and citraconic acids on a dropping mercury electrode.

Experimental

A. R. grade chemicals were used to prepare the solutions. The solutions of ligands were prepared in double distilled water. The solution of the metal ion was prepared by dissolving the calculated quantity of $CeCl_3 \cdot 6H_2O$ (Fluka A. G., Switzerland) in double distilled water and was standardized with EDTA⁵. The concentrations of Ce(III), potassium chloride and gelatin in the test electrolytic solution were fixed at 2.0 mM, 1.0 M and 0.01%, respectively. The concentration of the ligand was varied from 1.0 mM to 10.0 mM in each case. Ionic strength was fixed at $\mu=1.0$ adjusted with potassium chloride. Hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide were used to adjust the pH of the test solution at 2.75 ± 0.02 .

Polarograms were recorded on a automatic pen recording (C. I. C., Baroda, India) polarograph. The capillary used had an m value = 2.16 mg/sec and drop time 3.10 sec at 43.0 cm effective height of the

TABLE 1—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COMPLEXES IN 1.0 M POTASSIUM CHLORIDE

	Ce(III)	Crotonic acid		Cinnamic acid		Itaconic acid		Citraconic acid	
		1:1		1:1		1:1		1:1	
		25°	35°	25°	35°	25°	35°	25°	35°
Metal-ligand stability constant (log K)	Ce(III)	2.76	2.61	2.91	2.50	3.50	3.14	3.82	3.41
Change in enthalpy (ΔH) in k cal/mole	Ce(III)		-6.33*		-17.13*		-15.20*		-17.31*
Change in free energy (ΔG) in k cal/mole	Ce(III)	-3.78	-2.92	-3.99	-3.54	-4.80	-4.50	-5.24	-4.83
Change in entropy (ΔS) in cal/degree/mole	Ce(III)	-8.55	-11.07	-44.69	-44.77	-34.89	-34.90	-40.57	-40.52

* For the difference of 10°.

mercury. Dissolved oxygen was removed by passing pure nitrogen gas through the solution before recording the polarograms. An Elico digital pH meter (Model LI-120) was used to adjust the pH of the test solution at 2.75 ± 0.02 . All measurements were made at 25 and 35° by the use of thermostat.

Results and Discussion

Ce(III) gave a well defined reversible reduction wave at $pH 2.75 \pm 0.02^{6-7}$ in 1.0 M potassium chloride with 0.01% gelatin being used as a maximum suppressor. The log plot slope comes to the order of 20 ± 1 mV for Ce(III) and its complexes with all the four ligands indicating reversibility of the electrode process. The nature of the waves for metal ion and its complexes was found to be diffusion controlled as revealed from the straight line plots of i_d vs \sqrt{t} . The reduction potential of Ce(III) at $pH 2.75 \pm 0.02$ was -1.85 V vs SCE.

The half wave potential shifted to more negative value on increasing the concentration of ligand⁸. A Lingane treatment of the data revealed the formation of 1:1 complexes of Ce(III) with all the four ligands. The thermodynamic parameters were calculated from the thermodynamic relations⁹. Stability constants and thermodynamic parameters are tabulated in Table 1.

The order of stability constants of the complexes is

$$[Ce(III) - (crotonate)]^{2+} < [Ce(III) - (cinnamate)]^{2+}$$

$$\log k \quad 2.76 \quad 2.91$$

$$\text{at } 25^\circ$$

$$< [Ce(III) - (itaconate)]^1 < [Ce(III) - (citraconate)]^1$$

$$3.50 \quad 3.82$$

It is evident from the above that $[Ce(III) - (crotonate)]^{2+}$ is less stable than $[Ce(III) - (cinnamate)]^{2+}$. Both the ligands being monodentate in nature form simple coordination compounds while itaconic acid and citraconic acid being bidentate in nature form chelate compounds, which accounts for their higher stability over monodentate ligands¹⁰. The lower stability of the itaconate complex as compared to citraconate complex can be due to the presence of double bond in the ring¹¹.

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Polarographic Determination of Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Parameters of the Complexes of Nd(III) with Hydroxylamine, Hydrazine and Phenylhydrazine

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HYDROXYLAMINE, hydrazine and phenylhydrazine are the derivatives of ammonia which have been used as complexing agents by different workers¹⁻⁴. However, the use of polarography for the complexation study of rare earths with these ligands has not been reported. The stability constants and thermodynamic parameters of the com-